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Technical note on pointing jitter

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>The effect of pointing jitter is simulated for the CAIRT baseline instrument for comparison with radiometric requirements as well as to provide error spectra for subsequent use in the linear level-2 estimation of instrumental uncertainties.</p>		
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4	21-Feb-2024	Add new calculation for white noise pointing jitter in distinct frequency ranges Compute errors for all species and all ERS atmospheres and compare on basis of the latest L2 requirements as by end of CAIRT phase 0. Add pointing jitter error calculations for two ESA-supplied jitter time series.
5	4-Mar-2024	Add new calculation for white noise pointing jitter in one total frequency range. Add new calculation for uniformly distributed jitter noise.

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1. Introduction

The effect of pointing jitter is simulated for the CAIRT baseline instrument for comparison with radiometric requirements as well as to provide error spectra for subsequent use in the linear level-2 estimation of instrumental uncertainties.

2. Previous work

2.1. PREMIER

In the framework of ESA's PREMIER CORSA study, the effect of pointing jitter on the measured spectral radiances as well as on the retrieval was investigated (Dudhia, 2010, 2011; Kleinert et al., 2011; Friedl-Vallon and Kleinert, 2011).

In the first report (Dudhia, 2010), harmonic IFG distortions of effectively 40 m (30 m amplitude of the cosine) are applied with frequencies of 1, 3, 10, 30, 100, 300, 1k, 3k cycles/IFG for the chemistry mode instrument (2.5 cm MOPD). In the second report (Dudhia, 2011), more frequencies and a larger amplitude of 70 m (50 m of the cosine), as well as a subtraction of the mean from the distortion was applied. Some of the results were:

- a) Sensitivity to oscillations:
PREMIER IRLS chem mode (which fits CAIRT) sensitivities are most relevant for T (frequencies < 28 Hz) with errors around 0.17 K below 12 km, less relevant for O₃ and CH₄ (> 140 Hz) with max 5% in O₃@<10 km, and completely negligible for H₂O.
Other gases and z>20 km were not investigated. As far as altitude is concerned, it can be assumed that the errors are negligible above 20 km (they are already negligible between 12 and 20 km). As for other gases, it is difficult to extrapolate from the report's results. For the gases considered there, 70 m seems acceptable, since the pointing jitter component is much smaller than e.g. the gain error component.
- b) Sensitivity to pointing drift:
Influence of the direct effect (via IFG) is negligible, but a FOV widening is generated.
- c) Sensitivity to "realistic" jitter simulations from ESA:
Consistent with the results of the idealised simulations (a). Also: the PREMIER MRD specifies the jitter frequency range using a trapezoidal function (< 0.029 Hz and >714Hz no sensitivity, >0.07 Hz and < 286 Hz full sensitivity, linearly interpolated in between).

In the third reference (III) (Friedl-Vallon and Kleinert, 2011), the mathematics of pointing oscillations is described rigorously and error spectra are presented. Major points are considerations about possible mitigation strategies.

The last report (IV) (Kleinert et al., 2011) discusses the reference LOS (at IFG-maximum vs. mean LOS along the IFG), concluding that 'It is more realistic to assume that the mean LOS is known than to assume that the LOS at ZPD is known and used as a-priori information for the retrieval'.

2.2. MIPAS/Envisat

First results of a pointing jitter analysis were presented at the MIPAS/Envisat QWG meeting 2 in 2003 (Birk, 2003). In non-filtered IFGs of the raw data mode, an altitude-dependent jitter of 135 Hz was observed. A vertical pointing jitter amplitude of 100-200 m was derived. However, no clear sign of ghost-lines in the

spectrum could be identified (maybe there are also subsequent studies on this issue for MIPAS, revealing no clear sign of ghost-lines (A. Kleinert et al., pers. comm., 24-Feb-2023).

3. Baseline assumptions

For the following, the baseline assumptions are:

- Interferogram (IFG) maximum optical path difference (MOPD): 2.5 cm (0.2 cm⁻¹ resolution)
- 2-sided IFG
- IFG recording time: 7 s
- Spectra database: BRS (Baseline Reference Scenario)
- Back-transformation of perturbed IFGs: assume an ideal phase-correction, i.e. the real part of the complex spectrum is used (Dudhia, 2011)

4. Showcases for cosine perturbations

Figure 1 shows the ‘easiest’ case of a single (CO₂-Laserband) line disturbed by a cosine-like vertical perturbation during IFG-acquisition for perturbation amplitude of 500 m, frequencies of 0.1, 1, and 10 Hz and a tangent altitude of 15.7 km. The orange and blue lines in the 2nd and 3rd column are calculations for a pure linear assumption of the vertical gradient at each IFG position (orange, an assumption which is often made in analytical formulations of the problem) compared to the ‘real’ non-linear change of the IFG with altitude (blue). In the linear case, clearly the two ghost-lines of the main line, without a change of the amplitude of the main line can be seen. The ghost lines are negative since the cosine perturbation leads to an upward pointing at OPD=0, i.e. pointing to lower radiances. Non-linearity with altitude leads additionally to 2nd order ghost lines as well as to a loss of intensity of the main line (e.g. see bottom right panel in Figure 1).

The case an entire spectrum is perturbed by cosine-like jitters of the same frequencies as for the single line is demonstrated in Figure 2. These can be compared e.g. to the differences shown in Figure 3 (bottom) (Figs. 8.1, 8.2 of (Dudhia, 2010)) which was calculated for a tangent altitude of 10 km, a spectral resolution of 1.25 cm⁻¹ and a amplitude of 30 m. Taking these differences into account, the error spectra are of the same magnitude as the ones calculated here (right column of Figure 2).

Figure 1 Cosine perturbation of a single CO₂-line at 15.7 km tangent altitude. **Left:** altitude perturbation. **Middle:** spectra assuming a linear change of the IFGs with altitude (orange) and a realistic non-linear behaviour (blue). **Right:** differences with respect to the non-perturbed spectrum (perturbed-nonperturbed).

Figure 2 Same as Figure 1, but for an entire spectrum.

Figure 3 Taken from (Dudhia, 2010). Assumed pointing perturbations (top) and resulting error spectra (coloured, bottom) for the PREMIER IRLS dynamics-mode instrument (1.25 cm^{-1} resolution) at 10 km tangent altitude.

5. Monte-Carlo simulations for different perturbation frequency ranges

We have applied Monte-Carlo simulations to determine perturbed spectra for pointing jitter in five different frequency ranges: 0.01-0.1 Hz, 0.1-1 Hz, 1-10 Hz, 10-100 Hz and 100-1000 Hz. Within each of these ranges, 50 pointing perturbation curves along the IFG-axis have been determined. Examples of these perturbations are shown in Figure 4 to Figure 8. For each of these curves, 10 waves have been superimposed with random phases, frequencies and amplitudes. The phases are uniformly distributed within 0° - 360° , the frequencies uniformly within the respective frequency ranges, and the random amplitudes uniformly between 0-1 but normalized such that the sum of all ten amplitudes is equal 100 m.

The effects of these perturbations on the spectral radiances are summarized in Figure 9 to Figure 13. Here, for each of the 50 random perturbation curves, at each wavenumber the means as well as the standard deviations are shown for the five different perturbation frequency ranges. These are compared to the requirements on 'Radiometric Additive Error' (green in 1st and 2nd column) for the mean error spectra as well as to the requirement on 'Radiometric sensitivity (NESR)' for the standard deviations. In addition, the

application of a shift of the perturbation curve to its mean value (orange curves, 'AvgPTBeq0') compared to the original perturbation ('AvgPTBne0') is displayed. The first one, i.e. that the mean LOS over the interferogram is used as reference, has been the baseline for the PREMIER studies in (Dudhia, 2011) and has been identified as the appropriate reference in (Friedl-Vallon and Kleinert, 2011).

In general, with increasing frequencies, the error spectra are more and more 'blurred' through the ghost lines further away in the spectrum. However, the magnitudes of the mean as well as the standard deviation of the error spectra do not vary significantly between all five frequency ranges of perturbances. Compared to the radiometric additive error and the NESR requirements the error spectra's means and standard deviations are clearly smaller in most of the cases. Only for lowest tangent altitude the offset requirement is often exceeded in the lower wavenumber range as well as the NESR for the lowest wavenumbers. However, the requirement of $3 \text{ nW}/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr cm}^{-1})$ at the lowest altitudes has to be seen in relation to the absolute atmospheric radiances there of more than $1000 \text{ nW}/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr cm}^{-1})$.

Figure 4 Ten examples for altitude perturbations along the IFG axis from the (50) Monte-Carlo simulations. A number of 10 waves with random frequencies between 0.01 and 0.1 Hz, random phases and random amplitudes (normalized to a sum of all amplitudes of 100 m) are superimposed. The blue lines ('AvgPTBne0') show the original perturbation whereas the orange lines ('AvgPTBeq0') are shifted to the mean position over the IFG-recording time.

Figure 5 Same as Figure 4 but for a frequency range of 0.1-1 Hz.

Figure 6 Same as Figure 4 but for a frequency range of 1-10 Hz.

Figure 7 Same as Figure 4 but for a frequency range of 10-100 Hz.

Figure 8 Same as Figure 4 but for a frequency range of 100-1000 Hz.

Figure 9 Resulting means (1st and 2nd column) and standard deviations (3rd and 4th column) of the 50 error spectra from the Monte-Carlo simulations for different tangent altitudes and for perturbation frequencies between 0.01 Hz and 0.1 Hz. These are compared to the requirements on ‘Radiometric Additive Error’ (green in 1st and 2nd column) for the mean error spectra as well as to the requirement on ‘Radiometric sensitivity (NESR)’ (green and red in 3rd and 4th column) for the standard deviations. Blue indicates the use of perturbation curves with non-zero means (‘AvgPTBne0’) and orange the use of perturbations shifted to zero (‘AvgPTBeq0’), see, e.g., also Figure 4.

Figure 10 Same as Figure 9 but for perturbation frequencies of 0.1-1 Hz.

Figure 11 Same as Figure 9 but for perturbation frequencies of 1-10 Hz.

Figure 12 Same as Figure 9 but for perturbation frequencies of 10-100 Hz.

Figure 13 Same as Figure 9 but for perturbation frequencies of 100-1000 Hz.

6. White noise simulations for different perturbation frequency ranges

As a change to the previous versions (1,2) of this report, here we have introduced a new method to simulate white-noise jitter in the distinct frequency ranges 0.1-1 Hz, 1-10 Hz, 10-100 Hz and 100-1000 Hz. The method is provided here:

https://github.com/timsainb/noisereducer/blob/master/noisereducer/generate_noise.py as described here: <https://de.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/32111-fftnoise-generate-noise-with-a-specified-power-spectrum>

The pointing perturbations are normalized to a standard deviation of 25 m.

Examples of these perturbations are shown in Figure 14 to Figure 17.

The effects of these perturbations on the spectral radiances are summarized in Figure 18 to Figure 21. See the description of these figures as in chapter 5.

Figure 14 Five examples for altitude perturbations along the IFG axis from (left) for white noise between 0.1 and 1 Hz. Power spectral density (PSD) of these time-series (right).

Figure 15 Same as Figure 14 but for a frequency range of 1-10 Hz.

Figure 16 Same as Figure 14 but for a frequency range of 10-100 Hz

Figure 17 Same as Figure 14 but for a frequency range of 100-1000 Hz

Figure 18 Resulting means (1st and 2nd column) and standard deviations (3rd and 4th column) of the 50 error spectra from the white-noise simulations for different tangent altitudes and for perturbation frequencies between 0.1 Hz and 1 Hz. These are compared to the requirements on ‘Radiometric Additive Error’ (green in 1st and 2nd column) for the mean error spectra as well as to the requirement on ‘Radiometric sensitivity (NESR)’ (green and orange in 3rd and 4th column) for the standard deviations.

Figure 19 Same as Figure 18 but for perturbation frequencies of 1-10 Hz.

Figure 20 Same as Figure 18 but for perturbation frequencies of 10-100 Hz.

Figure 21 Same as Figure 18 but for perturbation frequencies of 100-1000 Hz.

7. Level-2 pointing jitter error estimation for white noise bands

7.1. Baselines

The error spectra, calculated as described in the previous section, have been used to derive vertical error profiles in a Monte-Carlo fashion. For this, the following baselines have been applied:

- **1d-linear profile retrieval**
- **All ERS atmospheres**
- Application of the gain-matrices to 30 random sample error spectra from **each of the four white noise pointing jitter frequency bands as defined in section 6.**
- White noise with **25 m standard deviation** pointing jitter error.

- **Vertical resolution** profiles are prescribed as defined in the **MATER L2-requirements** by adapting the vertical retrieval grid accordingly. **Threshold vertical resolution** is applied here throughout. (For goal vertical resolution: see plots in the zip-attachment)
- For **SF6**, **zonal coaddition** has been applied by dividing the estimated error by $\sqrt{28}$.
- **Horizontal resolution** profiles as defined in the MATER L2-requirements are considered by **dividing the estimated jitter-errors by the square-root of the number of along-track profiles**, i.e. the errors are multiplied by $\sqrt{50 \text{ km}/\text{along-track-resolution}(h)[\text{km}]}$, where ‘along-track-resolution’ is the altitude-dependent L2 goal or threshold requirement. **Threshold horizontal resolution co-addition** is applied here when the estimated jitter error is related to the vertical profile of the threshold L2-concentration- or temperature- requirements. (For goal horizontal resolution coaddition, which is applied when the errors are plotted wrt the goal L2-requirements, or no horizontal coaddition: see plots in the zip-attachment).
- To explore the effect of radiance offset retrieval for the mitigation of the jitter errors, the retrievals have been done (1) without joint retrieving an additive offset, (2) with joint retrieval of only one vertically varying offset and (3) **with retrieval of vertically as well as spectrally-varying radiance offset** (constant within each microwindow). The last option (3) is seen as the baseline and those results are shown here. Plots including also the other mw-databases are included in the supplemental plot-archive
- In addition to the **CAIRT baseline microwindow set** (**‘CAIRTstd’** as used in the D8 and D10 reports for 2d LPE error analysis and retrieval exercises), three more microwindow sets have been explored. The baseline shown here is ‘CAIRTstd’. (For results of all mw-set: see plots in the zip-attachment)
- The resulting altitude-dependent errors are plotted **relative to the requirement thresholds**. (Plots for requirement goal values are collected in the zip-attachment).

7.2. Results

The results of the retrievals for the different species and jitter-frequency ranges are shown in Figure 22 to Figure 26 for threshold T/vmr/vertical resolution/horizontal resolution.

The requirement threshold as per definition of the mean error within each altitude range is only exceeded for HCN in the jitter-frequency range 0.1-1 Hz. However, HCN is no primary species. Further, it is in discussion if not also for this lower frequency range an along-track coaddition is applicable.

For other gases only single profiles (often from a specific zonal region) at distinct altitudes exceed the threshold requirement, namely CO in the tropical UTLS at 100-1000 Hz, NO for single profiles in the lower stratosphere, PAN in the lowermost free tropical troposphere at lowest jitter frequencies.

Figure 22 Vertical profiles of estimated pointing-jitter errors relative to L2-threshold requirements for different jitter frequency ranges (columns) and different species (rows). Colored lines indicate the error-profiles for single ERS-atmospheres (orange: equatorial, green: mid-latitudes, blue: polar). The black lines indicate the mean of the all data points within the related altitude regions.

Figure 23 Same as Figure 22 for further species.

Figure 24 Same as Figure 22 for further species.

Figure 25 Same as Figure 22 for further species.

Figure 26 Same as Figure 22 for further species.

8. Simulated pointing-jitter time series

The following time series of pointing jitter have been evaluated:

'APE_Industry_noKBA.txt' and 'APE_total.txt'

8.1. APE_Industry_noKBA

The time series of the dataset 'APE_Industry_noKBA' comprising about one orbit is shown in Figure 27 and its frequency analysis in Figure 28. For calculation of tangent altitude variations from provided elevation angles, a satellite altitude of 800 km and tangent altitude of 10 km has been assumed.

From this time series, 30 samples have been chosen randomly (for each ERS atmosphere) as baseline for the determination of perturbation spectra. For the atmosphere 'april+45 (day)' Figure 30 presents the mean and standard deviations of the 30 samples of perturbation spectra.

To estimate the effects of the pointing jitter on the retrieval we used the same baselines as described in section 7.1. Results as shown in Figure 31 and Figure 32 indicate very small effects. Mind here the mean standard-deviation of the pointing jitter as noted in the figure caption is only around 2 m (over the sampling time of the IFGs) – compared to 12 m over the whole dataset (see Figure 27).

Figure 27 Time series of pointing jitter tangent altitude variability over one orbit for dataset 'APE_Industry_noKBA'.

Figure 28 Frequency analysis of the time series 'APE_Industry_noKBA'.

Figure 29 Distribution of pointing jitter for RPE of dataset 'APE_Industry_noKBA'.

Figure 30 Resulting means (1st and 2nd column) and standard deviations (3rd and 4th column) of the error spectra from the 30 randomly chosen pointing jitter sample of time series 'APE_Industry_noKBA' for different tangent altitudes. These are compared to the requirements on 'Radiometric Additive Error' (green in 1st and 2nd column) for the mean error spectra as well as to the requirement on 'Radiometric sensitivity (NESR)' (green and orange in 3rd and 4th column) for the standard deviations.

Figure 31 Vertical profiles of estimated pointing-jitter errors relative to L2-threshold requirements for different species for time series ‘APE_Industry_noKBA’. Colored lines indicate the error-profiles for single ERS-atmospheres (orange: equatorial, green: mid-latitudes, blue: polar). The black lines indicate the mean of the all data points within the related altitude regions.

Figure 32 As Figure 31 for further species.

1.1. APE_total

The timeseries of the dataset ‘APE_total’ comprising about one orbit is shown in Figure 33 and its frequency analysis in Figure 34. For calculation of tangent altitude variations from provided elevation angles, a satellite altitude of 800 km and tangent altitude of 10 km has been assumed.

From this time series, 30 samples have been chosen randomly (for each ERS atmosphere) as baseline for the determination of perturbation spectra. For the atmosphere ‘april+45 (day)’ Figure 36 presents the mean and standard deviations of the 30 samples of perturbation spectra.

For the retrieval error estimation (see Figure 37 and Figure 38) the results are very similar to those of the time series ‘APE_Industry_noKBA’ described in page 38.

Figure 33 Time series of pointing jitter tangent altitude variability over one orbit for dataset 'APE_total'.

Figure 34 Frequency analysis of the time series 'APE_total'.

Figure 35 Distribution of pointing jitter for RPE of dataset 'APE_total'..

Figure 36 Same as Figure 30 but for time series 'APE_total'.

Figure 37 Vertical profiles of estimated pointing-jitter errors relative to L2-threshold requirements for different species for time series 'APE_total'. Colored lines indicate the error-profiles for single ERS-atmospheres (orange: equatorial, green: mid-latitudes, blue: polar). The black lines indicate the mean of the all data points within the related altitude regions.

Figure 38 As Figure 37 for further species.

9. Level-2 pointing jitter error estimation for broad-band white noise

Here we report the results in case of white-noise for a broad frequency band from 0.1-500Hz. All retrieval baselines are the same as for the small band retrievals described in section 7.

The white noise has been calculated for a standard-deviation of the jitter amplitudes of 25 m. The distribution of jitter errors is shown in Figure 39.

Figure 39 Distribution of pointing jitter errors for the broad-band white noise case.

Figure 40 Vertical profiles of estimated pointing-jitter errors relative to L2-threshold requirements for different species for the broad-band white noise case of jitter errors. Colored lines indicate the error-profiles for single ERS-

atmospheres (orange: equatorial, green: mid-latitudes, blue: polar). The black lines indicate the mean of the all data points within the related altitude regions.

Figure 41 Same as Figure 40 for further species.

Figure 42 Same as Figure 40 but for the goal instrument specifications and the goal requirements.

Figure 43 Same as Figure 40 but for the goal instrument specifications and the goal requirements.

10. Level-2 pointing jitter error estimation for uniform noise

Here we report the results in case of uniform noise distribution along the IFG. All retrieval baselines are the same as for the small band retrievals described in section 7.

The uniform jitter noise has been calculated for jitter amplitudes of ± 25 m. The distribution of jitter errors is shown in Figure 44.

Figure 44 Distribution of pointing jitter errors for the uniform noise case

Figure 45 Vertical profiles of estimated pointing-jitter errors relative to L2-threshold requirements for different species for the uniform noise case of jitter errors. Colored lines indicate the error-profiles for single ERS-

atmospheres (orange: equatorial, green: mid-latitudes, blue: polar). The black lines indicate the mean of the all data points within the related altitude regions.

Figure 46 Same as Figure 45 for further species.

Figure 47 Same as Figure 45 but for the goal instrument specifications and the goal requirements.

Figure 48 Same as Figure 47 for further species.

11. Appendix: microwindow sets

Figure 49 CAIRT baseline microwindow set (CAIRTstd).

Figure 50 IMK MIPAS microwindow set (MIPImk).

Figure 51 ESA MIPAS microwindow set (MIPesa).

Figure 52 CAIRT large microwindow set(CAIRTlarge).

12. References

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